

STUDIES IN THE NAPHTHALENE SERIES. PART I. SYNTHESIS OF 1-KETO-5-BROMO (OR CHLORO-)-7:8- DIMETHOXY-1:2:3:4-TETRAHYDRONAPHTHALENE.

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1-Keto-5-bromo-7:8-dimethoxy-1:2:3:4-tetrahydronaphthalene and 1-keto-5-chloro-7:8-dimethoxy-1:2:3:4-tetrahydronaphthalene have been prepared. The ketones give their characteristic derivatives.

The object of the present synthesis was to synthesise some of the preliminary degradation products of thebaine in order to confirm the statements by different workers (*Annales*, 1924, 438, 34; *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1923, 123, 988; 1926, 2562). For this purpose the synthesis of 3:4-dimethoxy- β -ethyloctahydrophenanthrene was contemplated. This work is interrupted for want of facilities and so a brief note embodies the results so far achieved (*Abstract of Dissertations, Oxford University*, 1938, Vol. X). β -3:4-Dimethoxybenzoylpropionic acid and γ -3:4-dimethoxyphenylbutyric acid have been obtained in good yield according to the method of Haworth and Mavin (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1932, 160). The latter gives a quantitative yield of γ -6-bromo-3:4-dimethoxyphenylbutyric acid. This gives 1-keto-5-bromo-7:8-dimethoxy-1:2:3:4-tetrahydronaphthalene in 10-15% yield on treatment with phosphorus pentoxide. The use of the related chloro-acid improves the yield of the ketone (35%). The optimum conditions for the reaction have yet to be found.

EXPERIMENTAL.

β -3:4-Dimethoxybenzoylpropionic acid was prepared according to the method of Haworth and Mavin (*loc. cit.*) and crystallised from dilute acetic acid in prisms, m.p. 160-61° (*cf.* Haq, Kapur and Ray, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1933, 1088, who give m.p. 165°). This acid on Clemmensen reduction gave an oily product, which on rubbing and standing after the solution had been diluted with water, separated in slightly coloured beads and after distillation was recrystallised from dilute acetic acid at 0° in white shining prisms, m.p. 60-61° (m.p. 57-59°, Haworth and Mavin, *loc. cit.*).

γ -6-Bromo-3:4-dimethoxyphenylbutyric Acid.—The preceding acid (46.5 g., 1 mol.) was dissolved in acetic acid and bromine vapour (11.18 g., 1 mol.) diluted with dry air was passed through the solution when the bromo-

acid separated in prisms. On recrystallisation from acetone it melted at 139-40° (m.p. 135-36°, Haworth and Mavin). It is soluble in acetone, ethyl acetate, benzene, alcohol, less so in ether and insoluble in petroleum ether. It suffered no loss in weight on drying at 100° in *vacuo*. (Found: C, 47.1; H, 5.0; Br, 25.4; OMe, 18.5. Calc. for C₁₂H₁₃O₄Br: C, 47.5; H, 5.1; Br, 26.4; OMe, 20.5 per cent).

1-Keto-5-bromo-7:8-dimethoxy-1:2:3:4-tetrahydronaphthalene.—The preceding acid (5 g.) was dissolved in moist benzene (500 c.c.) and to the gently boiling solution phosphorus pentoxide (50 g.) was added in four instalments during 1½ hour. The solution, after refluxing for further ½ hour, was cooled and the mixture decomposed by adding ice to the solution at 0°. It was then made alkaline with sodium hydroxide and extracted with benzene. The dark oily residue (3 g.) from the washed and dried benzene layer was dissolved in alcohol and water added to it when some dark brown slimy product separated which was rejected. The clear solution on slow evaporation gave the ketone in thick crystals in 10-15% yield which after recrystallisation from dilute acetic acid had m.p. 91-92°. In a second experiment an attempt was made to purify the crude ketone (13 g.) by converting it into its semicarbazone but three products were obtained on fractional crystallisation of which the second was perhaps the mixture and the first only was the desired product: (i) m.p. 198° (1.8 g.); (ii) m.p. 188° (3 g.); (iii) m.p. 152-59° (6.5 g.). The last fraction gave values which showed that it was not the required product. (Found in material dried at 100° in *vacuo*: C, 45.4; H, 5.2; N, 7.4. C₁₃H₁₆O₃N₃Br requires C, 45.6; H, 4.7; N, 12.3 per cent). The ketone as isolated above after decolourising with charcoal from its methyl alcoholic solution crystallised in perfectly white long thick prisms, m.p. 91-92°. (Found in air-dried material: C, 50.9; H, 4.8; Br, 29.8; OMe, 21.3. C₁₂H₁₃O₃Br requires C, 50.5; H, 4.6; Br, 28.1; OMe, 21.8 per cent). The 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazone was obtained in clusters of orange needles, insoluble in alcohol and water, m.p. 220-25° (decomp.). The semicarbazone separated in square plates, m.p. 215° after crystallisation from alcohol. (Found: C, 46.2; H, 4.7; N, 11.8. C₁₃H₁₆O₃N₃Br requires C, 45.6; H, 4.7; N, 12.3 per cent).

The semicarbazone (1.7 g.) was hydrolysed by boiling with 20% aqueous oxalic acid solution (4 g. in 20 c.c. of water). After 25 minutes an oil began to separate which on further refluxing became crystalline and melted at 142-43°. It is soluble in sodium carbonate and gives no depression with the bromo-acid on admixture. The semicarbazone (0.5 g.) and oxalic acid (0.5 g.) were refluxed together in acetone solution (50 c.c.) for about 5 hours after which the straw-coloured solution was evaporated.

The residue, after adding water, was shaken three times with ether when unchanged semicarbazone separated from the aqueous solution (0.25 g.). The ether solution was washed with water, dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate and after removal of the solvent gave the bromo-dimethoxytetralone in amber-coloured aggregates of needles, m.p. 91-92° and gave no depression on admixture with a pure specimen of the ketone.

γ-6-Chloro-3 : 4-dimethoxyphenylbutyric Acid.—To a solution of β-3:4-dimethoxyphenylbutyric acid (10 g.), in acetic acid (25 c.c.), chlorine generated from potassium permanganate (5.8 g.) and diluted with carbon dioxide was passed slowly at 0°. The mixture was allowed to stand overnight when the chloro-acid (2.9 g.), m.p. 111-12°, separated in perfectly white needles. A further quantity was obtained from the solution by addition of water (total yield 9.9 g.). The acid was recrystallised from ether-acetone mixture in thick white prisms, m.p. 111-12°. (Found in material dried at 100° in *vacuo*: C, 55.5; H, 6.0; Cl, 13.7; OMe, 25.8. C₁₂H₁₆O₄Cl requires C, 55.6; H, 5.8; Cl, 13.7; OMe, 24.0 per cent).

1-Keto-5-chloro-7 : 8-dimethoxy-1 : 2 : 3 : 4-tetrahydronaphthalene.—The preceding chloro-acid (10 g.) was dissolved in benzene (800 c.c.) and treated with phosphorus pentoxide (75 g.) as in the previous case. The crude ketone was distilled in *vacuo*. The distillate crystallised from an alcohol-ether mixture in prisms and had m.p. 75°, unchanged after crystallisation from methanol (charcoal). (Found in material dried over P₂O₅: C, 59.1; H, 5.4; Cl, 15.1; OMe, 24.2. C₁₂H₁₄O₃Cl requires C, 59.9; H, 5.4; Cl, 14.8; OMe, 25.8 per cent).

The oxime, prepared in the usual way, crystallised in prisms from methanol in which it is difficultly soluble, m.p. 187°. (Found in material dried at 100° in *vacuo*: C, 56.4; H, 5.2; N, 5.4. C₁₂H₁₄O₃NCl requires C, 56.4; H, 5.5; N, 5.5 per cent). The 2 : 4-dinitrophenylhydrazone had m.p. 239-40°.

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